

A study on the potential application of neutron noise techniques to the TAPIRO reactor in support of fast reactor technology development

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ABSTRACT

Neutron noise analysis is an essential online monitoring technique used to characterize nuclear reactors, particularly well-established in thermal systems. Its extension to Gen-IV fast reactors faces significant technical challenges, considering the extremely short neutron generation time (under 0.1 μ s) in fast systems, which demands the precise tailoring of high-speed data acquisition systems and the adaptation of algorithms for data elaboration. The TAPIRO reactor, being a compact fast-spectrum critical facility, offers a controlled environment ideal for developing and validating noise methodologies representative of fast reactor conditions. Due to its small size and composition (copper reflector, high enrichment), TAPIRO's dynamics lead to shorter fission chains and reduced neutron population variance, which is consistent with its very short neutron lifetime. In this work, noise techniques are applied to simulated neutron counts generated using a detailed MCNP model of TAPIRO, allowing for an assessment of the applicability of noise techniques to this facility and providing guidance for planning future experimental campaigns at TAPIRO.

Keywords: TAPIRO Reactor, Noise Analysis, Prompt Decay Constant, MCNP Time Stamps

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutron noise analysis is a crucial technique for the online monitoring and characterization of nuclear reactors [1-3]. It involves measuring and analyzing the stochastic fluctuations of the neutron population, with correlations induced by the fundamental fission processes. The method is widely validated and applied in thermal systems, often requiring steady-state conditions and long measurement times to ensure good statistics. The associated modeling is typically based on the point kinetics approximation.

Noise techniques have been extensively applied to thermal reactors; see, for instance, the work on critical and subcritical assemblies in [4-5]. However, the experience gained in this framework cannot be directly applied to reactor concepts characterized by a fast neutron spectrum. Nonetheless, the extension of the domain of applications of noise techniques to fast reactors, in consideration of the R&D effort in this direction for Generation IV, is deemed crucial to exploit the potential of noise analysis for the design, characterization, and operation of future nuclear systems.

The extension of noise analysis to fast reactors presents challenges due to the extremely short neutron generation time (less than 0.1 μ s), which requires sophisticated, high-speed experimental devices for detecting neutron counts on the appropriate time scales. Furthermore, the standard mono-energetic models and integral parameter evaluations might need to be revised to account for the more complex spectral features of fast systems.

The TAPIRO reactor offers an almost unique solution to bridge this gap. As a compact, critical facility with a fast spectrum, TAPIRO provides an ideal, controlled environment to develop and validate noise methodologies representative of fast reactor conditions, largely avoiding spatial effects, due to the almost point-like behavior of the system, which was assessed in past studies [6] and more recently assessed with simulated pulsed source experiments [7].

Dr. Mario Carta, who was the director of the ENEA laboratory where TAPIRO is located until 2022, expressed a deep interest in the possibility of extending TAPIRO's activity towards neutron noise. Between 2020 and 2022, he actively worked to engage us in exploring this opportunity. The present

work constitute a significant step in the process of assessing the feasibility of performing noise analysis in TAPIRO: different neutron noise techniques are here applied to simulated neutron counts, generated with the Monte Carlo MCNP code, to clearly identify the limit of applicability of such methods and the necessary prescriptions for the data acquisition systems, in consideration of the characteristic time scales of this reactor.

2. NEUTRON NOISE TECHNIQUES APPLIED TO THE TAPIRO REACTOR

The neutron noise activity carried out in this work is based on the analysis of pulse trains, i.e., time series describing the time of neutron detections in a designated detector, sampled in two different detectors, adopting a modified version of MCNP6.2, following the methodology discussed in [8], assuming an external Cf-252 neutron source. The detectors are located in two different channels: radial channel no. 1 and tangential channel (see Figure 1 for the complete set of experimental channels in TAPIRO), at approximately the same distance from the fuel's outer surface. The detectors modelled are BF₃-filled ionization chambers with a cylindrical, non-negligible volume.

Figure 1. The irradiation channels of the TAPIRO [9]. The detectors are in the Radial Channel 1 and the Tangential Channel.

The timestamps generated have been analyzed using the noise techniques detailed in the following subsections to estimate the prompt decay constant and, therefore, the kinetic parameters of the TAPIRO reactor.

2.1. Feynman- α Method

This method starts with the selection of a time gate T , used to subdivide the simulation time into time bins. Then, the variance and mean of the detector neutron counts associated with different values of T are calculated, which are customarily defined as smaller than 0.1 seconds to avoid delayed neutron contributions. Finally, the Feynman distribution is constructed by plotting the (co)variance-to-mean ratio of the neutron counts minus one as a function of the gate values. If fission were absent, the neutron

detector counts would obey the Poisson distribution (i.e., variance equal to the mean), and the Feynman distribution would be null.

In a multiplying medium such as a reactor, the detector neutron counts are correlated through the fission chain and do not follow a Poisson distribution. The general Feynman distribution reads:

$$Y_{ij}(T) = \frac{Cov[c_i, c_j]}{E[c_i, c_j]} - 1 = \frac{\langle c_i c_j \rangle_T - \langle c_i \rangle_T \langle c_j \rangle_T}{\sqrt{\langle c_i \rangle_T \langle c_j \rangle_T}}, \quad (1)$$

where c_i, c_j are the random counts in the detectors; reducing to the case of one detector:

$$Y_i(T) = \frac{Var[c_i]}{E[c_i]} - 1 = \frac{\langle c_i^2 \rangle_T - \langle c_i \rangle_T^2}{\langle c_i \rangle_T}. \quad (2)$$

This distribution can be fitted by an analytical expression to obtain the prompt neutron decay constant α_p :

$$Y(T) = Y_\infty \left(1 - \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha_p T}}{\alpha_p T} \right). \quad (3)$$

2.2. The Power Spectral Density (PSD) Method

We start from the amplitude of the zero-power transfer function of the reactor, which takes the form:

$$|H(\omega)|^2 = \frac{1}{1 + (\omega/\omega_c)^2}, \quad (4)$$

for large frequencies ($\omega \gg \lambda_j$), having defined the cutoff frequency $\omega_c \equiv (\beta_{\text{eff}} - \rho)/\Lambda$. The cross-correlation power spectral density (CPSD) is defined as the Fourier transform \mathcal{F} of the convolution of two neutron detector counts $c_1(t)$ and $c_2(t)$ in a fixed time interval T :

$$CPSD(\omega) = \mathcal{F}\{c_1(t), c_2(t)\} = \mathcal{F} \left\{ \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T c_1(t) c_2(t + \tau) dt \right\} = \mathcal{F}\{c_1(t)\} \mathcal{F}^*\{c_2(t)\}. \quad (5)$$

The zero-power transfer function amplitude $|H(\omega)|^2$ can also be written in terms of the two detector neutron counts $c_1(t)$ and $c_2(t)$ as:

$$|H(\omega)|^2 = \frac{CPSD(\omega)}{\bar{c}_1 \bar{c}_2} \frac{1}{2D/F_0}, \quad (6)$$

where \bar{c}_i is the average neutron detector i count rate, $D = \frac{\bar{v}(\bar{v}-1)}{\bar{v}^2}$ is the Diven factor, and F_0 is the integral fission rate in the core. The combination of the previous two expressions for $|H(\omega)|^2$ enables to link the cross-correlation (or the auto-correlation in the case of a single detector) power spectral density of the neutron noise and the core kinetic parameters, since the resulting expression can be fitted with a Lorentzian function of the form

$$f(\omega) = \frac{x_1}{1 + (\omega/x_2)^2} + x_3, \quad (7)$$

and the kinetic parameters can be obtained as: $\beta_{\text{eff}} - \rho = \sqrt{\frac{2D}{F_0} \frac{1}{x_1}}$, $\Lambda = \frac{\beta_{\text{eff}} - \rho}{2\pi x_2}$.

2.3. Rossi- α Method

The Rossi distribution quantifies the probability that a pair of neutron captures (doubles) occurs within a fixed time interval Δt ; this distribution includes two components exhibiting different statistical characteristics. The first contribution represents the pair of neutron captures from uncorrelated

neutrons, i.e., neutrons originating from different fission chains and/or other nuclear interactions, and thus obeying Poisson statistics. This component is constant since the probability of a second neutron detection at time Δt after the first detection is independent of the first detection. The second component represents the pair of neutron captures from correlated neutrons, i.e., originating from the same fission chains. This component shows an exponential decay, as the probability of a second detection at time Δt after the first detection decays according to the prompt neutron decay constant α_p .

The Rossi distribution can thus be expressed as:

$$P_R(\Delta t) = C + Be^{-\alpha_p \Delta t}. \quad (8)$$

The above formula is used to fit the Rossi distribution obtained from the elaboration of the experimental (here, simulated) data, to obtain the prompt neutron decay constant. Similarly to the Feynman- α method, the fitting interval is arbitrary, which introduces uncertainties in calculating the prompt neutron decay constant.

3. NEUTRON NOISE RESULTS ON TAPIRO

In this section, the results of applying noise techniques to the simulated timestamps in TAPIRO are briefly presented. To better understand the physical motivation behind these results, it is essential to note that the characteristics of TAPIRO, specifically the copper reflector, the small core size, and high enrichment, lead to shorter (time-wise) fission chains. The high concentration of U-235 increases the probability of fission per neutron collision, but the small physical size of the core results in higher neutron leakage. The likelihood of neutrons escaping the core before inducing additional fissions increases, effectively terminating fission chains prematurely. The copper reflector intensifies this effect by allowing more neutrons to leak. Consequently, it is expected to observe that fluctuations in the neutron population are reduced, leading to lower variance in neutron counts over time, which is consistent with the very short neutron lifetime ($\sim 40\text{-}50$ ns, see [10]).

3.1. Feynman- α Method

Figure 2 shows the Feynman- α distribution for time gates in the range $1 \leq T \leq 200$ μs for both detectors and, as an example, the fit performed for one of the detectors in the radial channel (detector1) with the corresponding residuals, while Table I reports the fitted prompt decay constant obtained, with associated uncertainty.

Figure 2. Feynman- α distribution for time gates in the $1 \leq T \leq 200 \mu\text{s}$ range (left) and fitted FY curve with corresponding residuals for detector1 (right). On the left, the variance-to-mean ratio $Y_i(T)$ is shown for each detector, and the covariance-to-mean ratio $Y_{12}(T)$ is shown for both detectors.

Table I. The fitted prompt decay constant α_p based on the Feynman- α method.

	α_p [s^{-1}]	σ_α [s^{-1}]	σ_α [%]
FY₁	65240.3	82.5	0.13
FY₂	65592.7	92.6	0.14
FY₁₂	65063.1	73.7	0.11

As the differences in fission chain lengths and neutron count variance affect the shape of the Feynman- α curve, observing Figure 2 reveals that short fission chains and reduced fluctuations cause the curve to rise sharply and reach saturation quickly. The rapid rise indicates that correlations in neutron counts decay swiftly because the neutron population returns to equilibrium rapidly after a fluctuation. The early saturation reflects the limited variance due to the short fission chains.

3.2. The Power Spectral Density (PSD) Method

The spectra calculations were performed with buffer size $N = 8192$ and time bin size $\Delta t = 10^{-6}$ s. This choice means a spectral resolution of $\Delta f = 122$ Hz and a Nyquist frequency of 500 kHz. Choosing a buffer size N as a power of 2 improves the computational efficiency of the numerical implementation of the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT).

Figure 3 shows the Auto- and Cross-correlated PSD curves using $\Delta t = 1 \mu\text{s}$ and buffer size $N = 8192$, and the Lorentzian fit for detector1. The fitted parameters are given in Table II.

Figure 3. The Auto- and Cross-correlated PSD curves (left) and the fitted Lorentzian and the residuals for the Auto-correlated PSD of detector1 (right).

Table III. The fitted prompt decay constant α_p based on the PSD method.

	α_p [s^{-1}]	σ_α [s^{-1}]	σ_α [%]
APSD₁	66783.4	183.4	0.27
APSD₂	67293.8	175.8	0.26
CPSD₁₂	64955.3	97.0	0.15

Examining the APSD curve, the results in TAPIRO indicate a lower amplitude at low frequencies compared to the values typically observed in thermal systems. This is because the short fission chains result in less correlated neutron behavior over longer time scales, reducing power at these frequencies. Rapid changes in neutron populations spread the power over a wider frequency range, causing the APSD curve to display a broader frequency spectrum with a flatter distribution across frequencies.

Regarding the CPSD curves, as the core exhibits reduced spatial correlations due to short fission chains and high neutron leakage, this leads to lower coherence between detectors at low frequencies in the CPSD, indicating weaker spatial correlations across the core.

The larger magnitude of α_p , corresponding to a faster neutron population decay, also affects the high-frequency behavior, with a higher cutoff frequency (~ 100 kHz) where the APSD/CPSD begins to decline and shows significant power at higher frequencies.

3.3. Rossi- α Method

The Rossi- α distribution was calculated using a time bin $\Delta t = 1 \mu\text{s}$ and an upper limit of $200 \mu\text{s}$. Figure 4 shows the Rossi-alpha distribution and the exponential fit for each detector, as well as the merged distributions. Additionally, a focus on detector 1, along with its corresponding residuals, is presented. In Table III, the resulting fitted values of α_p are reported.

Figure 4. Rossi- α distribution and the exponential fit for each detector and for both merged (left) and Rossi- α distribution and the exponential fit residuals for detector1 (right).

Table III. The fitted prompt decay constant α_p based on the Rossi- α method using $\Delta t = 1 \mu\text{s}$.

	α_p [s^{-1}]	σ_α [s^{-1}]	σ_α [%]
Rossi₁	67202.9	251.39	0.37
Rossi₂	67724.1	263.26	0.39
Rossi₁₂	67165.0	201.75	0.30

3.4. Typical Prompt Decay Constant for Fast Reactors

The results obtained through the noise analysis of these simulated experiments provide useful information to guide the planned experimental campaign on noise analysis in TAPIRO. Moreover, the values of the prompt decay constant obtained for TAPIRO are consistent with previous analysis of fast neutron facilities. For example, in [11], the prompt decay constant for Godiva, a bare U-235 critical assembly, is reported in the order of 10^5 s^{-1} for reactivity levels in the range 30-300 pcm, and also in [12],

a variety of fast reflected and bare critical assemblies were considered, with prompt decay constants of $\sim 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$. More recently, in [13], the prompt decay constant of the subcritical VENUS-F reactor (a representative zero-power facility for LFR ADS, featuring 30% enriched uranium fuel, lead assemblies, and a lead reflector) was evaluated. The prompt decay constant was measured to be $\sim 2 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, with a corresponding neutron lifetime of $1 \mu\text{s}$.

The picture that emerges from the literature indicates that the prompt neutron decay constant of SFRs and LFRs, with 20-30% uranium or MOX fuel, ranges between 10^5 and 10^5 s^{-1} , with a typical neutron lifetime of $0.1\text{-}1 \mu\text{s}$. This range of values supports the representativity of TAPIRO as a facility in support of fast neutron reactor physics studies.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The neutron noise analyses performed for the TAPIRO reactor, using the Feynman- α , Rossi- α , and PSD techniques, provide a coherent and internally consistent characterization of the prompt neutron decay constant and the underlying neutron dynamics of the system. Across all three methods, the extracted α_p values fall in the expected range for a compact, highly enriched, fast-spectrum assembly with a copper reflector. The short neutron generation time, the rapid decay of correlations in both the time and frequency domains, and the sharp early saturation of the Feynman- α curve all confirm the presence of very short fission chains, dominated by high neutron leakage and limited reflector effectiveness. The Rossi- α and PSD methods reinforce this interpretation: both show fast exponential and high-frequency decay components consistent with the fast neutron lifetime of approximately $40\text{-}50 \text{ ns}$, and with prompt decay constants of the order $10^4\text{-}10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, in line with historical measurements of similar fast critical assemblies.

The analyses demonstrate that neutron noise methods remain highly effective for characterizing the prompt neutron dynamics of fast-spectrum systems, provided that detector modeling, fitting ranges, and numerical parameters are handled with care. The results obtained here provide a reliable reference benchmark for future uncertainty assessments, numerical parameter sensitivity studies, and potential experimental campaigns involving the TAPIRO reactor in support of Gen-IV fast reactors development.

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